

Sample Name: PA 6-9 μm

Material: Polyamide (Nylon-6,6)

Size: 6-9 μm

Production Partner: Wessling

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 1% particles are between 6-9 μm
 - 99% are between 1-5 μm
- Particles have a rounded, irregular morphology
- 9.1×10^{10} particles per gram
- 16260 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- S, P and Rb contaminants detected by ICP-MS
 - P and Rb $< 1 \mu\text{g/g}$
- No changes due to milling observed in Raman spectrum.
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PA spectrum with no evidence of degradation

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- $D50_v$: Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- $D50_N$: Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
3.06	2.67	2.45	2.33	2.11	2.31	9.1 10^{10}	16260

Morphology (using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using ICP-MS provided by Wessling)

Element	Concentration
S	25 $\mu\text{g/g}$
P	1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Rb	<1 $\mu\text{g/g}$

Raman Spectroscopy (provided by Wessling)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

